

Electrospinning Hagfish Intermediate Filament Protein and Fabrication of Aligned Fiber Bundles

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Note: This is a working manuscript for ongoing research. As characterization methods come online for our lab and more data is collected, it will be added into this work and the draft will be updated.

Abstract

We report an electrospinning process for recombinant hagfish intermediate filament protein (rHIF) and demonstrate a complete pathway from protein solution to aligned, mechanically characterized fiber bundle. Pure rHIF solutions could not be electrospun without poly(ethylene oxide) (PEO) as a spinnability aid, a requirement explained by the low solution viscoelasticity of the protein alone and the need for a carrier polymer to exceed the critical Deborah number for stable jetting. Glutaraldehyde vapor crosslinking (90 min) significantly improved bundle stiffness and strength in both dry and hydrated conditions, establishing crosslinking as a necessary step for mechanically robust bundles. Together, these results provide a reproducible processing pathway from recombinant protein to macro-scale fibrous construct with tunable mechanical properties, and establish a foundation for future functionalization including conductive polymer coating.

1. Introduction

Hagfish produce one of nature's most remarkable defense mechanisms: a rapidly deployed slime that is composed of a mucus network reinforced by protein threads of exceptional mechanical performance. These threads are assembled from hagfish intermediate filament (HIF) proteins, which form coiled-coil dimers that self-assemble into highly ordered filaments. Studies of native hagfish slime threads have demonstrated extraordinary combinations of high extensibility, toughness, and the ability to absorb significant energy before failure, mechanical properties that substantially exceed those of most synthetic and biological fibers tested under comparable conditions.^{1,2,3}

Recombinant expression of hagfish intermediate filament proteins (rHIF) in *E. coli* provides a tractable route to access this protein class without relying on the hagfish itself. Solution processing of rHIF enables fiber fabrication via techniques such as electrospinning, which is well established for producing continuous micro- and nanoscale fibers from polymer dopes.⁴ However, proteins present well-documented challenges for electrospinning compared to synthetic polymers: limited chain entanglement, sensitivity to solvent environment and humidity, and the potential for

secondary structure changes during processing.^{5,6} For globular or partially unfolded proteins in particular, high solution concentration alone is insufficient to produce stable jetting because the solutions lack the long relaxation times and elastic character needed to suppress Rayleigh instabilities in the elongating jet.

A common strategy to overcome this limitation is blending the target protein with a high-molecular-weight carrier polymer such as poly(ethylene oxide) (PEO), which provides the required viscoelastic character through chain entanglement. This approach has been demonstrated for a range of proteins including silk fibroin,⁷ collagen,⁸ and keratin,⁹ and in each case even modest carrier polymer additions enable stable jetting from protein solutions that cannot be electrospun alone. PEO in particular is attractive because it is biocompatible, water-soluble, and can be removed by aqueous dialysis after fiber formation, yielding a predominantly proteinaceous fiber.

Beyond individual fiber formation, hierarchical assembly of electrospun mats into bundle structures offers a practical route toward materials with mechanical properties approaching those of native protein fibers. Rolling electrospun mats into cylindrical bundles concentrates the fiber mass, increases handleability, and creates a geometry amenable to uniaxial mechanical testing. Crosslinking of the constituent fibers within the bundle is a further means to tune mechanical properties, with glutaraldehyde vapor crosslinking being widely used for protein-based materials due to its ability to form covalent intermolecular bridges via Schiff base chemistry without requiring liquid-phase immersion.¹⁰

In this work we establish an electrospinning process window for rHIF, characterize the requirement for PEO co-spinning in terms of solution viscoelasticity and the Deborah number, and demonstrate fabrication and mechanical characterization of aligned rHIF fiber bundles. Glutaraldehyde vapor crosslinking is evaluated as a method for improving mechanical robustness in both dry and hydrated conditions. The results provide a reproducible foundational processing pipeline for rHIF-based fiber materials.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials

2.1.1 Protein and polymer

Recombinant hagfish intermediate filament protein (rHIF) was provided by Prof. Justin Jones (Utah State University). The protein was expressed in *E. coli*, purified, and shipped for use in these experiments. Poly(ethylene oxide) (PEO; Sigma-Aldrich) was used as a spinnability aid and was obtained in two molecular weights: 300 kg/mol (lot T23L016) and 1000 kg/mol (lot T29I006).

2.1.2 Solvents and reagents

1,1,1,3,3,3-Hexafluoro-2-propanol (HFIP; cat. 003409) was purchased from Oakwood Chemicals. Formic acid (FA; lab grade, 98%; cat. A0470831) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Glutaraldehyde solution (25% in water; cat. 4282171; Sigma-Aldrich) was used for vapor-phase crosslinking. Glycine (Sigma-Aldrich, cat. G8898) was

prepared as a 100 mM aqueous quench solution. DI water was obtained from a Millipore Direct-Q system.

2.2 Preparation of spinning dopes

rHIF and PEO were dissolved at target concentrations (wt% w/v) in HFIP or HFIP:FA solvent mixtures with stirring for 3 hours prior to electrospinning to ensure full solvation and homogeneity. Two initial exploratory solutions — 5 wt% rHIF in neat HFIP and 5 wt% rHIF in neat FA — were prepared to assess the solubility and spinnability of the protein in each solvent system individually.

In neat HFIP, rHIF dissolved readily with stirring, producing uniform, gray, opaque solutions after approximately 2 hours. An additional hour of stirring was applied before spinning. In neat FA, the protein solvated at a comparable rate but exhibited persistent foaming, phase separation when left undisturbed, and progressive darkening of the solution over time, reaching a peak black color at approximately 24 hours. Solutions aged beyond 24 hours failed to produce fibers during electrospinning, consistent with denaturation or chemical modification of rHIF in neat FA. On this basis, all FA-containing dopes were used within 6 hours of preparation. Characterization of the degradation mechanism using Raman spectroscopy and SDS-PAGE is planned for future work.

Subsequent formulations used mixed HFIP:FA solvent systems (Table 1) to slow the evaporation rate of the solvent during fiber formation. PEO was incorporated in most formulations as a spinnability aid; PEO-free rHIF controls were tested at multiple concentrations to establish the necessity of PEO for stable jetting. As discussed in Section 3.1, PEO-free rHIF solutions failed to produce continuous fibers regardless of concentration. Additional samples explored the impact of rHIF concentration, solvent ratio, and PEO molecular weight on fiber formation.

Table 1: Formulations used in this work.

Formula tion ID	rHIF (wt% w/v)	PEO (wt% w/v)	PEO MW (kg/mol)	Solvent system
F1	5	—	—	100% HFIP
F2	5	—	—	100% FA
F3	7.5	0.5	1000	85:15 HFIP:FA
F4	7.5	0.5	1000	75:25 HFIP:FA
F5	15	0.25	1000	85:15 HFIP:FA
F6	15	0.25	300	85:15 HFIP:FA

2.3 Electrospinning setup and run logging

Electrospinning was performed using a commercial StonyLab electrospinner (SL001626) housing a syringe pump, grounded rotating drum collector, high voltage source, and temperature and humidity sensors. A rastering motor distributed the electrospun fibers evenly across a defined collector width. For each run, the following

parameters were recorded: applied voltage, volumetric flow rate, tip-to-collector distance, needle gauge, drum rotational speed, raster settings, and environmental conditions (temperature and relative humidity). Representative anchor runs are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: Representative electrospinning runs.

Run date	Needle	Voltage (kV)	Distance (cm)	Flow (mL/min)	Drum (rpm)	Temp (°C) / RH (%)
2026-01-07	22 ga	25	15	0.5	200	22–25 / [Insert RH]
2026-04-20	20 ga	10–15	20	0.01–0.018	2500–3000	19.6–26 / [Insert RH]

2.4 Mat collection and bundle fabrication

Nonwoven mats were electrospun onto aluminum foil on the drum collector, removed by hand, and dried at room temperature overnight to allow residual solvent to evaporate. Bundles were fabricated by rolling mats perpendicular to the direction of drum rotation until a cylindrical geometry of approximately 300–400 μm outer diameter and ~ 25 cm length was achieved. Rolling was performed with fibers oriented axially along the bundle length, producing a construct with preferential fiber alignment along the tensile axis. Outer bundle diameter was measured using optical microscopy with a calibrated Zeiss light microscope and confirmed by laser profilometry.

2.5 PEO removal

Where PEO removal was performed, bundles were soaked in DI water for 48 hours with water exchanges every 12 hours to extract the sacrificial polymer by diffusion. Successful removal was assessed qualitatively by dimensional and handling changes. Quantitative verification by Raman spectroscopy, comparing the PEO C–O–C stretch (~ 1100 cm^{-1}) before and after dialysis, is planned for future work.

2.6 Crosslinking via glutaraldehyde vapor

Where crosslinking was applied, bundles were placed in a sealed desiccator with 4 mL of 25% glutaraldehyde solution at room temperature for 90 minutes. Glutaraldehyde vapor crosslinks primary amines on lysine residues and protein N-termini via Schiff base formation, generating covalent intermolecular bridges without requiring liquid immersion — an important practical advantage for preserving bundle geometry during treatment.¹⁰ Following exposure, samples were quenched in 100 mM glycine solution for 10 minutes to react any remaining aldehyde groups, then rinsed three times in DI water and either stored in room-temperature DI water or dried for long-term storage.

Crosslinking was not applied to all samples. rHIF bundles are water-insoluble after electrospinning due to solvent removal and conformational changes induced during the spinning process, so crosslinking is not strictly required for aqueous handling. However, crosslinking was evaluated as a means of improving mechanical stiffness, strength, and

dimensional stability under hydration, which is the focus of the mechanical characterization reported in Section 3.4.

2.7 Characterization

Fiber and bundle morphology. Individual electrospun fiber diameter was assessed from optical micrographs acquired on a Keyence laser profilometer. Images were calibrated in ImageJ and diameters measured at five locations per image. Values are reported as mean \pm SD. Bundle outer diameters (dry and wet) were measured separately by optical microscopy and laser profilometry using ImageJ at two locations per image.

Mechanical testing. Uniaxial tensile testing was performed using a CellScale Univert equipped with a 2.5 N load cell. Bundles were mounted with a gauge length of 30 mm and strained to failure at 100 mm/min. Force–displacement data were converted to engineering stress and strain using a circular cross-sectional area calculated from the measured bundle diameter (360 μm for dry samples, 630 μm for wet samples, reflecting swelling upon hydration). Young’s modulus was extracted by linear regression of the initial loading region: 0–2% strain for dry samples, and 5–20% strain for wet samples to account for the large toe region characteristic of hydrated fibrous assemblies in which fiber slack is progressively recruited before load-bearing commences.

3. Results

3.1 Electrospinning outcomes and process window

Electrospinning outcomes were assessed on three criteria: generation of a continuous, stable jet; deposition of a cohesive nonwoven mat removable from the collector; and reproducibility across runs. Pure rHIF solutions in either neat HFIP or neat FA failed to produce continuous fibers at all concentrations tested, including up to 25 wt% (w/v). Instead, unstable jetting, dripping, and spray-like deposition were predominant, demonstrating that high solution concentration alone was insufficient to enable stable electrospinning.

This outcome is understood in terms of solution viscoelasticity. While viscosity is necessary for electrospinning, it is not sufficient — the solution must also possess sufficient elasticity to sustain elongational deformation without jet breakup. The Deborah number ($De = \lambda/t_c$, where λ is the polymer relaxation time and t_c is the jet elongation timescale) provides a useful framework: when $De \ll 1$, the solution is viscous-dominated and the jet breaks up; when $De \geq 1$, elastic stresses stabilize the jet against Rayleigh–Plateau instabilities.¹¹

Globular and partially unfolded proteins such as rHIF form compact, relatively inextensible molecular structures with short effective relaxation times in solution, placing pure rHIF dopes in the low- De , jet-unstable regime even at high concentrations. High-molecular-weight PEO, by contrast, forms highly entangled random coil networks with long relaxation times, and blending modest quantities of PEO (0.25–0.5 wt%) into the rHIF dope shifted the solution into the elastically stabilized jetting regime. This is

consistent with the established role of carrier polymers in electrospinning of protein solutions, where small additions of PEO or other high-MW polymers reliably enable stable jetting from protein solutions that are otherwise unspinnable.^{7,8,9}

Environmental sensitivity was also observed: runs conducted at higher relative humidity produced less cohesive mats, consistent with the known sensitivity of HFIP-based systems to moisture uptake slowing solvent evaporation and reducing jet solidification rate.⁶

3.2 Fiber and bundle morphology

Fibers were electrospun from a solution of 15 wt% rHIF and 0.25 wt% PEO (1000 kg/mol) in 85:15 HFIP:FA (v/v). This formulation proved the most robust across repeated runs, balancing the fast evaporation rate of HFIP with the slower-evaporating FA component, which modulates jet drying kinetics and improves processability. Following optimization across multiple runs, the conditions that produced the most consistent fiber formation were: 10 kV applied voltage, 20 cm tip-to-collector distance, 20-gauge needle, 0.01 mL/min flow rate, 3000 rpm drum collection speed, and chamber conditions of 19.5–20.5 °C and 52–54% relative humidity. The sensitivity of fiber quality to relative humidity within this narrow window is consistent with the known susceptibility of HFIP-based electrospinning systems to moisture uptake.⁶

Individual electrospun fiber diameter averaged $1.90 \mu\text{m} \pm 0.81 \mu\text{m}$, while ribbon-type fibers averaged $4.09 \mu\text{m} \pm 0.39 \mu\text{m}$ in width. Electrospun mats contained a mixture of circular cross-section fibers and collapsed ribbon-like structures, as seen in Figure 2. Ribbon formation arises from the rapid evaporation of HFIP during spinning: the fiber exterior solidifies into a skin while solvent remains trapped internally, and as the interior solvent subsequently evaporates, the resulting pressure differential causes the fiber to collapse into a flattened ribbon morphology. This skin-collapse mechanism is well documented for electrospun fibers produced from rapidly evaporating solvents.¹²

Figure 1: Optical microscope image of individual electrospun rHIF fibers and ribbons. Mean \pm SD: Fibers = $1.90 \mu\text{m} \pm 0.$; ribbons = $4.09 \mu\text{m} \pm 0.39 \mu\text{m}$.

3.3 Bundle fabrication and vapor-phase crosslinking

Electrospun mats were successfully rolled into bundles with dry outer diameters of 300–400 μm (mean 361 μm) and lengths of approximately 25 cm. Figure 2 is a light microscope image of what a rolled rHIF bundle looks like after PEO removal. Figure 3 is a histogram of the distribution of hand-rolled bundle diameters in both dry and hydrated states. Bundles were very robust and could be mounted for tensile testing and transferred through aqueous processing steps without loss of structural integrity. After PEO removal by water soaking (48 h with exchanges), bundles retained their cylindrical form but exhibited a mean increase in diameter to 644 μm when placed in water, consistent with hydration-driven swelling of the protein matrix. Glutaraldehyde vapor crosslinking did not produce visible dimensional changes in dry bundles but qualitatively reduced swelling relative to uncrosslinked controls under aqueous conditions.

Figure 2: Representative dry rHIF bundle.

Figure 3: Distribution of individual electrospun rHIF fiber bundles measured by optical microscopy. The average (a) dry bundle diameter is 361 μm while the average (b) wet fiber bundle diameter is 644 μm.

3.4 Mechanical properties of rHIF bundles

The mechanical properties of rHIF bundles were characterized under both dry and hydrated conditions to evaluate the effect of glutaraldehyde vapor crosslinking on bundle integrity. A table of the average values of the Young's Modulus and maximum stress of the bundles can be seen below in Table 3.

Table 3: Mechanical properties of rHIF bundles under dry and wet conditions, testing in triplicate. Young’s modulus (E) and maximum tensile stress reported as mean \pm SD.

Sample	Mean E (MPa)	SD E (MPa)	Mean max stress (MPa)	SD max stress (MPa)
Crosslinked dry	924.7	685.6	31.2	9.8
Uncrosslinked dry	285.1	182.7	19.1	1.1
Crosslinked wet	4.6	3.6	2.2	1.3
Uncrosslinked wet	1.6	0.3	0.9	0.5

Figure 4: Stress–strain curves for rHIF bundles under (a) dry and (b) wet conditions. Solid lines: crosslinked; dashed lines: uncrosslinked. Multiple replicates shown as overlapping curves (lighter = additional replicates). Diameter assumed circular: 360 μm (dry), 630 μm (wet).

Under dry conditions, crosslinked bundles exhibited substantially higher stiffness than uncrosslinked counterparts, with a mean Young’s modulus of 924.7 ± 685.6 MPa compared to 285.1 ± 182.7 MPa, and a mean maximum tensile stress of 31.2 ± 9.8 MPa versus 19.1 ± 1.1 MPa. Dry bundle stress–strain curves (shown in Figure 4) display a characteristic steep linear region at low strains followed by failure at relatively low extensibility ($< 25\%$ strain), consistent with the behavior of densely packed, dry protein fiber assemblies. Uncrosslinked dry bundles showed lower replicate-to-replicate variability than crosslinked bundles, likely reflecting heterogeneous crosslink density from diffusion-limited glutaraldehyde vapor penetration through the dense bundle.

Upon hydration, both crosslinked and uncrosslinked bundles underwent a dramatic transition in mechanical behavior. Stiffness dropped by two to three orders of magnitude (to 4.6 ± 3.6 MPa in crosslinked samples, and 1.6 ± 0.3 MPa in uncrosslinked samples)

and extensibility increased markedly, with some wet samples sustaining strains exceeding 200% before failure. Maximum tensile stress was reduced to 2.2 ± 1.3 MPa and 0.9 ± 0.5 MPa respectively. Crosslinked wet bundles were nonetheless significantly stiffer and stronger than uncrosslinked wet bundles, demonstrating that glutaraldehyde crosslinking provides meaningful mechanical reinforcement even under hydrated conditions. These values are similar to work with silk protein fiber bundles manufactured in a similar way, which had an ultimate tensile strength of 4.7 MPa.¹³ The large region visible in the wet stress–strain curves reflects progressive recruitment of fibers as slack is taken up, a behavior commonly observed in hydrated fibrous biomaterials such as collagen and tendons.¹⁴

4. Discussion

4.1 Formulation requirements and the role of PEO

The inability of pure rHIF solutions to generate continuous fibers, even at concentrations approaching 25 wt%, reinforces the established distinction between bulk viscosity and solution viscoelasticity as determinants of electrospinning success. Synthetic high-molecular-weight polymers typically provide both viscosity and elasticity through chain entanglement, but globular or partially unfolded proteins do not entangle in the same way: even concentrated solutions have short effective relaxation times and low De , placing them in the viscous-dominated, jet-unstable regime. Inclusion of PEO at modest concentrations introduces long-relaxation-time chains that shift the solution into the elastic-dominated jetting regime without requiring the protein to entangle. This interpretation is consistent with the broader protein–PEO electrospinning literature.^{7,8,9}

The choice of PEO molecular weight and concentration is an important design variable. Higher MW PEO provides longer relaxation times at lower mass fractions, which minimizes the residual PEO required to dialyze out post-electrospinning. The present work used 300 and 1000 kg/mol PEO as direct experimentation of the electrospinning success or not. In future works, systematic rheological characterization, such as measuring viscosity and relaxation time as a function of PEO content and MW, would provide more insight for formulation optimization and help identify the minimum effective PEO content.

4.2 Crosslinking: Mechanical outcomes and bundle architecture

Glutaraldehyde vapor crosslinking provided clear and consistent mechanical benefits under both dry and hydrated conditions. The improvements are most practically significant under hydration, where uncrosslinked bundles are highly extensible and weak. The high replicate-to-replicate variability observed in crosslinked dry samples relative to uncrosslinked controls likely reflects heterogeneous crosslink density — a known limitation of vapor-phase crosslinking of dense fibrous constructs, where diffusion of the aldehyde vapor through a ~ 360 μm diameter bundle creates a crosslink density gradient from the surface inward.¹⁰ Future work could address this by systematically varying exposure time, reducing bundle diameter, or applying a mild swelling pretreatment to improve vapor penetration.

The assumption of a solid circular cross-section in stress calculations is an approximation that likely introduces systematic overestimation of true fiber-bearing area, since the bundle contains void space between fibers. Cross-sectional imaging by SEM would allow better estimation of the effective load-bearing area and would improve the accuracy of reported modulus and stress values. Despite this limitation, the relative comparison between crosslinked and uncrosslinked samples within the same batch remains valid.

4.3 Fiber morphology and the ribbon formation mechanism

The mixture of circular fibers and collapsed ribbons observed in the electrospun mats reflects the fast evaporation kinetics of HFIP (boiling point 58°C), which creates a rapid fiber solidification front. When the exterior skin solidifies before the interior solvent has fully evaporated, the pressure drop upon interior solvent loss causes the fiber to collapse axially, producing a ribbon. The presence of FA in the solvent blend (boiling point 101°C) reduces the mean evaporation rate of the mixture and may partially suppress ribbon formation compared to pure HFIP; however, the dominant solvent in the blend is HFIP, so the ribbon-forming tendency remains. Controlling the HFIP:FA ratio, drum-to-needle distance, and temperature/humidity are all potential levers for shifting the fiber morphology distribution toward predominantly circular cross-sections.

4.4 Future directions

The present work establishes the core processing pipeline from rHIF solution to aligned, mechanically characterized fiber bundle. Several important directions remain for future work. First, the PEO removal step should be verified quantitatively using Raman spectroscopy (PEO C–O–C stretch at $\sim 1100\text{ cm}^{-1}$) to confirm the extent of extraction and to establish whether any PEO remains in crosslinked versus uncrosslinked bundles.

Second, the crosslink density and its distribution through the bundle cross-section should be characterized, ideally by varying glutaraldehyde exposure time and correlating with mechanical outcome. FTIR or Raman spectroscopy could provide semi-quantitative tracking of imine bond formation as a function of treatment conditions.

Third, and of particular interest for future applications, the bundle architecture reported here is well-suited to surface functionalization via conductive polymer deposition. Polydopamine (PDA) surface priming followed by polypyrrole (PPy) electro-polymerization has been demonstrated on protein-based fiber substrates and offers a route to electrically conductive, mechanically compliant constructs relevant to bioelectronics and soft robotics. The bundle geometry and the crosslinking conditions developed in this work provide a defined starting point for such functionalization and is an interesting space to explore in future work.

5. Conclusion

This work demonstrates a complete processing pathway from recombinant hagfish intermediate filament protein (rHIF) solution to aligned, mechanically characterized fiber bundle. Stable electrospinning of rHIF required the addition of high-molecular-weight

PEO as a spinnability aid, a necessity rationalized by the low solution viscoelasticity of pure rHIF dopes and the requirement to exceed a critical Deborah number for stable jet elongation. The ribbon fiber morphology observed in mats is attributed to the skin-collapse mechanism driven by rapid HFIP evaporation.

Glutaraldehyde vapor crosslinking for 90 minutes significantly increased both stiffness and maximum tensile stress of the resulting bundles in dry and hydrated conditions. Crosslinked wet bundles were markedly stiffer and stronger than uncrosslinked wet bundles, establishing crosslinking as a necessary step for bundles intended to be used or processed under aqueous conditions. The within-group variability in crosslinked samples points to diffusion-limited crosslink density gradients as a current limitation, motivating future optimization of the vapor-phase treatment.

The processing pipeline established here provides a reproducible and characterizable foundation for subsequent functionalization. Surface modification with conductive polymers and broader mechanical and electrical characterization are identified as priority next steps toward rHIF-based functional fiber materials.

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